

TEST AND SAFETY CONCEPTS FOR REINFORCEMENT MATERIALS WITH TIME DEPENDANT RESISTANCES

André Weber, Schoeck Bauteile GmbH, Germany, andre.weber@schoeck.com

ABSTRACT

Novel reinforcement materials made of glass fiber or carbon fiber composite plastic exhibit partially significant differences between short-term and long-term values, especially with respect to tensile strength and bond. This paper presents different ways to predict characteristic values for these properties for the design period. The semi-probabilistic safety concept of the current and forthcoming family of modern performance based standards as well as many years of experience with German and foreign approval authorities are taken into account. For different actions like sustained load, variable load and accidental load, the influence of exhibition conditions and time is discussed. The process of degrading in a composite is described and a model to describe the results is presented.

For each of these actions different concepts are known from guidelines and scientific papers. These concepts are discussed and related to the possible test setups. These different concepts are underlined with real data examples for tensile strength and bond for different products from GFRP. The pros and the cons of tests with accelerated ageing, tests with load and accelerated ageing and Time to failure tests are discussed for the different properties.

KEYWORDS

Safety concept; test setup; accelerated ageing; GFRP rebars

INTRODUCTION

Internationally and especially in Europe, Canada and the US intensive research has been carried out for several decades on concrete components with fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) reinforcement. Successfully carried out references and practical projects can be found in many areas of structural and civil engineering [1]. However, in the last two decades, in Germany the focus of research and application has been on the external reinforcement of concrete members, especially with carbon fiber composite (CFRP) laminates [2]. Another major research focus especially in Germany and Austria is textile concrete, which started with the Special Research Centers SFB 528 and SFB 532 in Dresden and Aachen [3,4,5,6] and is currently being further intensively researched in the large-scale project C³. Textile concrete TRC is about FRP reinforcements, which are mostly processed to grid-like fabrics by textile processing and are especially used as directional internal reinforcement in thin-walled concrete components. For this form of novel reinforcement elements, too, the application raises the questions of time-dependent material behavior [7]. In the relevant European standards and guidelines, novel internal reinforcement materials have been regulated only sporadically. Therefore, in legal terms, the only way to use them in Germany is via approvals in individual cases (ZiE), general building authority approvals (abZ) and, throughout Europe, European Technical Approvals (ETA). For this purpose, it is necessary to provide evidence in a suitable form of all the properties relevant to the planned area of application and the duration of use.

This often represents a major time and financial hurdle for manufacturer, planners, builders and users in the application of the innovative reinforcement materials.

For all these approval variants, a characteristic value of a resistance with a defined statistic is first required for this purpose. For the determination of the short-term resistance, the evaluation of a defined number of ideally standardized tests is sufficient. For the characterization of the long-term properties, however, further considerations have to be taken into account in order, on the one hand, to represent the planned application period realistically within an acceptable time span, and, on the other

hand, to be able to make a statistically sound statement on the probability of failure [8]. To this end, various methods and verification procedures have been developed and successfully applied in the context of the approval procedures for FRP reinforcements in recent years [9,10,11,12].

For most concrete members reinforced with internal reinforcement the percentage of sustained loads is high. Other members like slabs on ground or barrier walls show a high percentage of live loads. In this case also the question of fatigue can be posed. (This question is not handled in this paper) In addition there is a certain probability for an accidental load. The sum of all tests performed for qualification or certification shall represent these different actions as near as possible and shall have resistances as an output, suitable for the design with the accepted design codes.

Several of these methods have also been used successfully for connectors and sandwich anchors made of FRP [14]. Here in the meantime several EADs have been worked out by the EOTA and other technical organizations.

The long-term strength f_{fk100} [13] described in this article is for example a load which can be transferred with a certain probability for a time span of 100 years and not a characteristic residual strength after a certain aging but the characteristic resistance to all static (in particular long-term and short-term) loads. Essential for these methods is the (realistic) representation of the environmental influences with regard to the medium and temperatures used, as well as the selection of the load levels and test times matched to the prediction model used.

Actions to FRP reinforcement

Generally, actions on FRP reinforcement are the same as on steel reinforcement. But of course, some of the resistances are different and can't taken as obvious. So the evidence has to be shown in suitable tests. But first there is a look into the different applications and their actions. The first diagram is the action in a typical residential building. Dead load represents a high percentage of the load, while live load represents a smaller part while the maximum of the loads is present in less than 10% of the total service life. Figure 1 and 2 are sketched by the author to illustrate possible load scenarios.

Fig.1: actions in a residential building

In different applications there are different actions to be expected. In figure 2 we see a simplified action chart in a barrier wall. Most of the time there is a low action on the rebars. Crack limitation as well as thermal actions are the main actions to consider. Accidental actions seem to be the main actions.

Fig. 2: actions in a barrier wall

So the qualification tests should represent such actions as resistance against sustained loads, live loads as well as accidental loads in an adequate way. Over all there is an action which is not even considered as an action for steel reinforcement: Alkalinity. This inherent property of concrete is protecting steel against corrosion as well as attacking embedded FRPs

Time-dependent material behaviour

To show that properties remain constant over the time, often residual strength tests after different aging and/or loading conditions are usual. A typical result of these tests is shown in the next figure as envelope of several tests performed.

Fig. 3: Different residual strength envelope curves for different ageing conditions

The higher the load during the test, the earlier the residual creases. Test durations between 1000 and 10000 h are usual. This diagram is sketched by the author to illustrate the general behaviour of GFRP.

Durability and tensile strength under load

Most FRPs are known not to be able to maintain their high strength values over arbitrary times [13,15,16]. The so-called "creep rupture" phenomenon is observed under constant loads. The simplest way to describe this phenomenon is as follows. The greater the load on an element, the shorter the

service life under a constant load. The resistance can drop quite differently depending on the material, processing, raw materials used, temperature and humidity. Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) and the chemically very similar basalt fibre reinforced plastics are considered to be particularly sensitive in this respect [16,13,17]. With CFRP, too, the long-term resistance is not the same as the short-term resistance, whereby in particular the plastic matrix and the internal bond between fibres, and not so much the fibres themselves, are subject to time-dependent damage [16,13,17].

In a unidirectional composite, several hundred thousand individual fibres are usually used largely in parallel. Figure 3 shows an enlarged longitudinal section of such a composite. You can see here the predominantly parallel alignment of the fibres, but also some fibres with deviations from the longitudinal axis.

Fig. 4: Longitudinal and transverse section through a pultruded unidirectional glass composite (fibre diameter approx. 0.025 mm)

All fibres have a statistically distributed strength and, depending on the processing, a statistically narrower or wider distributed different orientation in the rod. Now, depending on the load and temperature, there is a different probability of breakage for the individual fibres. Such single fibre fractures can be compensated within very short distances by neighbouring fibres and the released force can be redirected to the original fibre [15]. This mechanism works differently depending on the fibre-matrix adhesion and thus affects different sized areas in the longitudinal direction of the reinforcement elements. Temperature, humidity and alkalinity can influence fibre-matrix adhesion in different ways over time [15]. If there is a local accumulation of defects in the individual fibres, the undamaged continuous fibres are disproportionately loaded by the necessary rearrangements, which in turn increases the probability of fracture. This leads to a locally accumulated accelerated damage progression, which finally results in a progressive failure of the entire reinforcement element. A typical series of creep curves under high load, showing these events by visible increases in total displacement (vertical axis), is shown in Figure 5. The total displacement is composed of the deformation of the bar and the slip in the concrete anchorage.

Fig. 5: creep test under permanent load in 40° C moist concrete

In this diagram, creep curves with a largely constant slope are visible after a degressive adaptation phase. Furthermore, however, at some times both smaller increases in displacement and, in part, a subsequent change in the slope of the creep curve can be observed. After such increases, the curve finally transitions into a progressive range, which ends in a break with the generation of larger creep paths. This transition can take place at different speeds depending on the degree of damage.

In short term test not all these rearrangement processes can proceed in time, Therefore different failure modes with higher loads and lower deformation are observed.

For a safe design, it is necessary to determine the limits of the tensile load-bearing capacity with sufficient accuracy, taking into account durability aspects for the respective material in the corresponding environment and for the planned service life. Testing and safety concepts for the characterisation of different reinforcement systems are presented in the following sections. Some guidelines or standards from the North American region [16,17] attempt to describe this behaviour without examining the individual reinforcement material by means of general factors for material groups (GFRP, CFRP). Depending on the product, place of use (interior/exterior), planned service life and component temperature, this procedure must be critically questioned either against the background of economic efficiency or in order to achieve a sufficient level of safety. Newer developments of the ACI 440 Design guideline show the results of the recent discussions.

Durability tests are required according ACI or CSA guidelines [16,17]. The loads for the durability tests, with a test strain of 0.3 %, are usually still below the or near the permitted limit for permanent loads. On the other hand creep rupture tests are tested at room temperature in air [19].

Exposure to media and artificial ageing under load

In order to represent the decades-long use of FRP reinforcement in concrete, different approaches are taken in the literature. In North American research, the pure bars are usually exposed to an artificial concrete pore solution consisting of 0.9 g NaOH, and 4.2 g KOH per litre of water and saturated CaOH with a pH value of 12.7 [19,17]. In Europe, the similarly composed but 10 times more concentrated solution with 9g NaOH and 42g KOH as well as CaOH saturation (also called "Masthoff solution") with a pH value of 13.7 is usually used [10]. With all aqueous solutions, however, the question arises as to whether the pH value alone actually sufficiently describes the effect on the rod. It is usually reported that although the pH value in the solution is lower than in a real concrete, the effect in the solution is stronger [10,16]. A possible explanation for this could be the lack of mobility of the

harmful ions in real concrete pores. Thus, a transfer of the results of a test of the pure reinforcement material in alkali solution to real concrete seems to be connected with discussions. A way out of this dilemma is the use of real concrete as surrounding intermediate medium during artificial ageing. For the investigation of the permanent tensile bearing behaviour, specimens are surrounded with a cylinder of concrete and tested in a water bath [10,12]. The specimen in the creep tensile test should be long enough to produce at least one transverse crack under load. This activates the bond in this test set-up and a practical multi-dimensional stress state develops in the rib or in the vicinity of the concrete cracks. The test setup is shown in Figure 6:

Fig. 6: Realistic loading and environmental conditions of rebar in a cracked concrete prism

The concrete used for this purpose should be produced with a CEM I Portland cement with sufficient alkalinity. Furthermore, it should not contain any substances such as microsilica in order to allow the concrete to absorb moisture and thus a practical, limited further transport of moisture. Thus, the impact in the test rig is very comparable to a very aggressive real impact in practical application [10]. Therefore, the only thing left to discuss when using moist concrete is the possibility of an accelerated test execution and its evaluation.

40° C is defined as the reference temperature for all applications. This value seems quite high in comparison with the average temperatures in Germany of about 10° C. Taking summer radiant heating into account, the temperatures in exterior, unshaded building components can certainly rise to over 60° C in concrete. Taking into account a time-temperature shift of 10 K per logarithmic decade, a weighted average temperature of 35-40° C is obtained for 7 cm thick sunlit façades [21,22] or cantilevered building elements. With this weighting, the entire standing time spectrum of a year for the respective temperatures is shifted to a reference temperature in each case. This is then shifted until the total service life is one year. This results in a weighted or representative temperature. The reference temperature of 40° C as well as a service life of 100 years was also determined by the expert committee of the DIBt for non-metallic reinforcement within the framework of the approval procedure for the general building authority approval (Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung) Z-1.6-238 [9] also in accordance with the Eurocode [24].

For typical applications of FRP reinforcement, it is necessary to prove resistance for a service life of 100 years at 40° C in moist concrete. A service life of 50-100 years is also assumed for reinforcement [13,16,17].

Detection methods for long-term resistances

The long-term resistance of the material required for safe use and presented here is the resistance to static actions (permanent and variable) over the entire service life. This value is to be verified with the associated fracture probability as characteristic resistance.

In order to simplify a later design, these two types of actions are added together on the safe side. This concept was accepted by DIBt in previous approval procedures [9,10].

In the following, three concepts with equivalent certainty in the statement are presented and discussed.

Detection method for resistance against accidental loads

A resistance to short-term loading at the end of a service life is explicitly not described here. The similarity between the test concept in northern America (low load during ageing and residual strength test afterwards) and the action chart for a barrier wall (fig 2) shows, that such test concepts may be sufficient to determine resistance especially against accidental loads. On the save and conservative side the long-term resistance described above can also be used for this.

Determination of long-term values by extrapolation of creep curves

One method of determining safe data for 100a 100-year service life is to extrapolate tests at 40° C and increased load with shorter service lives in the direction of lower loads and longer service lives at the same temperature. It is important to correctly describe the relationship between service life and stress. In relevant standards such as DIN 53768 and EN 705 [23,25], a linear dependence between the logarithm of the stress and the logarithm of the service life to failure is described. However, the possibilities of extrapolation are usually limited to a certain logarithmic time ratio of 1.5 - 2. This leads to testing times of more than one year for usual lifetimes of 50 to 100 years. In addition, a sufficient number of test points would have to lie within this time period at the same time. Since only break points may be evaluated as test points according to this method, runs can bind a larger number of test stands. This method is thus difficult to plan overall and would require a large number of finely graded trials.

Shorter test times are easier to realize, but will cause a greater uncertainty in the extrapolation. In order to increase the probability of information for such longer time ratios, the above-mentioned committee of experts (SVA) has therefore imposed a further condition on the test performance and demanded a further series at 60° C. The requirement for this supplementary test series is to ensure sufficient linearity up to a stress value comparable to the expected stress value. The requirement for this supplementary test series is to prove sufficient linearity up to a stress value - comparable to the expected extrapolation value. This is to show that the curve does not bend downwards with longer service lives or higher degrees of damage. An evaluation of the respective test series according to the error square method also enables a quantitative evaluation of the linearity parallel to the extrapolation of the results. Here, limits were added by the DIBt via the applicable standards such as EN 705, ISO 9080 and DIN 53768 [23,25,26] to further increase the safety of the extrapolation. Thus, according to the above-mentioned SVA, the 40° C straight line may be extrapolated by 2.2 decades if the variance $R^2 > 0.85$ is proven for the 60° C straight line [10].

Fig.7: Extrapolation method at 40° C with additional linearity check for 60° C

It is also important to clearly separate the transition from short-term failure to long-term failure. Long-term values may only be included in the statistics from the transition into the linear range [10,12]. Otherwise, the extrapolation value could be influenced in the unsafe direction. The linear ranges of the test period given for the reinforcement system Combar are 50-5000 hours for 40° C, and for 60° C between 25 and 5000 hours.

Furthermore, with this extrapolation method, it is also possible to specify a fracture probability via a simple statistical procedure. For this evaluation, the 5 % quantiles of the probability of tensile failure or bond failure were also determined. Thus, assuming a statistical distribution, it is possible to determine the stress at which 95 % of the specimens achieve a service life longer than 100 years under the specified conditions. This value is the sought-after characteristic value of the tensile strength. In the series of tests carried out within the framework of the Combar approval, for example, a value of 580 N/mm² was determined [9].

Determination of the long-term values with the time-temperature shift

In this method, too, samples are tested in a creep test rig according to figure 6. However, the test series at 40° C is dispensed with and the values for 40° C are inferred from the values at 60° C and shortened time. It is important in this context that the straight line can only be shifted horizontally between two similar states, i.e. on a line with the same stress (cf. Fig. 7). Basically, a state of higher temperature and shorter time corresponds to a state of longer time and lower temperature. For this, the amount of the time-temperature shift must also be known. This is ideally to be determined by experiments according to 3.1. However, in the literature and the relevant standards, there is only a small spread in the time-temperature shift for the materials used [13,16,17]. When shifting from high temperatures towards lower temperatures, this is on the safe side if one assumes the time-temperature Vv shift determined according to section 3.1 for a very durable and temperature-stable system of 10 K/dec. This means that by increasing the temperature by 20 K from 40° C to 60° C, a service life extension by a factor of 100 can be simulated [12]. Thus, at 60° C and 8800 h service life, the values for 100 years and 40° C can be read. Here, too, the least square method must be used to determine the mean value and 5 % quantile curve. Only in this way can a reliable determination of the characteristic strength be made from the scatter of the break points by means of statistical evaluation.

Figure 8: Time-temperature shift for predicting the 100-year lifetime values

This method was applied in the approval extension Z1.6.-238 from d=16mm in the first approval to the diameters 8, 12, 16, 20 and 25mm [12]. Here, tests were carried out at 60° C for the smallest (d=8mm) and largest diameters (d=25mm). Compared to the 40° C tests, at 60° C damage can be

detected more quickly and the linearity of the resulting straight line can be assessed. Figure 8 shows the tests for different diameters in a diagram. It is interesting to note that the long-term resistance is obviously the same for all diameters tested. In short-term tests, smaller diameters sometimes show significantly higher strengths. A general reduction of the short-term value by a certain factor does not do justice to the material behaviour. Instead, a certain limit stress seems to be determinable for each material as a function of temperature, humidity and service life. With otherwise linear elastic material behaviour, this results in a constant characteristic strain, which enables a design similar to that of reinforcing steel with diameter-independent values.

Figure 9: Time-to-failure diagram as function of sustained load and diameter in wet concrete

Determination of long-term values with a combination of prevalent tests

In the new Eurocode (FprEN1992-1 Annex R) a simple evaluation is proposed to determine safe design values. Therefor the influence of alkalinity (long term test with or without load), time (creep rupture tests in air) and temperature (40 degree rated service temperature instead of room temperature is described in three different factors. Multiplied they give a conservative evaluation of the f_{fk100a} value

$$f_{fk100a} = f_{fk} \times C_e \times C_c \times C_T \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

With f_{fk} characteristic short term strength

C_e : percentage of residual strength after alkaline ageing

C_c : percentage of creep rupture strength for 1 million h

C_T : temperature reduction for short term testing performed at 23°C instead of 40°C (0,8 if no other values are available)

It seems obvious, that a combination of all these influences in one test will lead to higher values, but as these test results are widely available and in some guidelines also combined with minimum values. In so far this proposal makes it possible to connect different safety concepts worldwide.

Discussion

Safe resistance values

An important point of discussion here is whether the characteristic value of the long-term tensile strength determined according to the methods mentioned in this paper only applies to the proportion

of permanent loads, as recommended in [16], and whether the characteristic short-term tensile strength should be used for variable loads, for example.

Fig. 10: Residual strength under realistic (outside natural weathering) conditions (see also fig.:3)

For higher strains than tested and longer service life it seems that the residual strength concept does not give enough safety (fig. 9)

A simple estimation shows that the long-term value is also a reasonable limit for variable loads. Assuming that the ratio of permanent loads is about 50 % of the total action and. The variable loads would act about 10 % of the time. This means that the creep would then not act 100a but one logarithmic decade less, namely 10a. Then the resistance would realistically only increase by $50 \% \times 15 \% = 7.5 \%$ with a slope of the resistance curve (see also Figure 7) of 15 % per logarithmic decade.

The approach of short-term strengths does not appear to make sense in principle and tends to be on the unsafe side. A smaller reduction of the strength against accidental loads such as impacts or earthquakes still needs to be researched. Here, the short-term resistance after storage with a low load could be used. On the safe side, long-term resistance is also recommended here [10].

In all other applications, and here temporary buildings with a service life of around one year are also explicitly meant, safety is played with, if short-term resistances are used for dimensioning. In the resistance curves of figure 7 it quickly becomes clear that on a logarithmic scale 1 year is closer to the long-term than to the short-term value.

Conclusion

The verification methods explained in this article have all been applied in various approval procedures for GFRP reinforcement or GFRP fasteners in recent years, resulting in a general approval or a individual case (one time) approval. European Assessment Documents (EADs) are currently being prepared by various parties, which are based partly on these findings and partly on other concepts.

For all test methods, it must be ensured that a reliable characteristic value can be determined for the test parameter. The time-dependent material behaviour must be determined realistically by a suitable concept for extrapolation of the measurements. With the methods presented here "Extrapolation of creep curves" , "Time-temperature shift" and "Combination of prevalent tests" as well as sensibly determined or specified partial safety factors, the engineering world is able to fulfil all requirements for the use in semi-probabilistic design standards with a semi-probabilistic safety concept.

Under the umbrella of CEN, TC250 is finishing the revision of the current EC2 fprEN1992-1(2023). Glass fibre reinforcement is included here in Annex R.

The German Committee for Reinforced Concrete (DAfStb) is finishing a (complete) design, testing and application guideline for textile reinforcement and FRP reinforcement.

With the safe values tested according to the above concepts or lying on the safe side and being very conservative with a combination of already known tests a more extensive use of this new type of reinforcement, will be possible in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Mufti, M. Onofrei, B. Benmokrane, N. Banthia, M. Boulfiza, J. Newhook, B. Bakht, G. Tadros, and P. Brett: Durability of GFRP Reinforced Concrete in Field Structures.
- [2] *DAfStb Technische Regel* Betonbauteile mit geklebter Bewehrung: 2012-03
Verstärken von Betonbauteilen mit geklebter Bewehrung Beuth Verlag Berlin 2012
- [3] Curbach, M., Jesse, F.: Eigenschaften und Anwendung von Textilbeton. *In: Beton- und Stahlbetonbau* 104 (2009), Heft 1, S. 9-16.
- [4] Hegger, J., Horstmann, M., Voss, S., Will, N.: Textilbewehrter Beton. Tragverhalten, Bemessung und Anwendung. *In: Beton- und Stahlbetonbau* 102 (2007), Heft 6, S. 362-370.
- [5] Lorenz, E., Schütze, E., Schladitz, F., Curbach, M.: Textilbeton - Grundlegende Untersuchungen im Überblick. *In: Beton- und Stahlbetonbau* 108 (2013), Heft 10, S. 711-722.
- [6] Hegger, J., Will, N., Curbach, M., Jesse, F.: Tragverhalten von Textilbewehrtem Beton. *Beton- und Stahlbetonbau* (2004).
- [7] Spelter, A., Rempel, S., Will, N., Hegger, J.: Prüfkonzept zur Untersuchung des Dauerstandverhaltens von textilbewehrtem Beton. *In: Bauingenieur* 92 (2017), Heft 9, S. 364-369.
- [8] Bau-Überwachungsverein (BÜV e.V.) Hrsg. Tragende Kunststoffbauteile: Entwurf – Bemessung – Konstruktion Springer Vieweg 2014
- [9] Z-1.6-238 Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung “Bewehrungsstab Schöck ComBAR aus glasfaserverstärktem Kunststoff, Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik Z-1.6-238 vom 8.12.2008
- [10] Schießl, P. et al.: Gutachterliche Stellungnahme zum Antrag der Firma Schöck beim DIBt auf allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung einer Betonbewehrung aus GFK-Stäben mit der Handelsbezeichnung „ComBAR“; Teil A 07/051/1.1.1 vom 31.03.2007
- [11] Schießl, P. et al.: Gutachterliche Stellungnahme Teil A2 zum Antrag der Firma Schöck beim DIBt auf allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung einer Betonbewehrung aus GFK-Stäben mit der Handelsbezeichnung „ComBAR“; Teil A2: Ergänzungsuntersuchungen zu Grundlagenfragen 07/051/1.2.1 vom 5.12.2007
- [12] Schießl, P. et al.: Gutachterliche Stellungnahme zum Antrag der Firma Schöck beim DIBt zur Zulassungserweiterung der Betonbewehrung aus GFK Stäben mit der Handelsbezeichnung „Combar“ 09/285/1.1.1 2013
- [13] Federation international de beton (fib) Hrsg. Bulletin 40. FRP reinforcement in RC structures, fib, Lausanne, 2007
- [14] Pahn, M.; Schnell, J. Einfluss der Verbundtragwirkung bei mehrschichtigen Stahlbetonwandtafeln mit innen liegender Wärmedämmung, *Beton und Stahlbetonbau* 106, Heft 8, 2011, 551-560
- [15] Ehrenstein, G.W.; Pongratz, S.: Beständigkeit von Kunststoffen, Band 1. Hanser Verlag München 2007
- [16] ACI 440.1R15 Guide for the Design and Construction of Structural Concrete Reinforced with FRP Bars, ACI Farmington Hills 2015
- [17] CSA-S806-10 Design and Construction of Building Components with Fiber-Reinforced Polymers, Canadian Standards Association, Mississauga, Canada. Canadian Standards Association 2010
- [18] Shahidi, F.: Bond degradation between FRP bars and concrete under sustained loads. PhD thesis, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, 2003

- [19] ACI 440.3R04 Guide Test Methods for Fiber-Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) for Reinforcing or Strengthening Concrete Structures, ACI Farmington Hills 2004
- [20] RILEM: RILEM technical recommendations for the testing and use of construction materials. London: E & FN Spon 1994.
- [21] Fouadh, N.: Gutachtliche Stellungnahme Nr.: GS 109 Betreff: Untersuchungen zum Temperaturverhalten von dreischichtigen Stahlbetonwandtafeln mit Schöck Hohlwandankern HWA aus glasfaserverstärktem Kunststoff, Hannover 14.07.2009
- [22] Schießl, P. Knab, F.: Gutachterliche Stellungnahme Auswirkungen von in Deutschland auftretenden Temperatureinwirkungen in Stahlbetonvorsatzschalen auf die Dauerhaftigkeit und Tragfähigkeit des ComBAR Thermoanker TA München 09/234/1.1.2
- [23] DIN 53768:1990-06 Extrapolationsverfahren für die Bestimmung des Langzeitversagensverhaltens von glasfaserverstärkten Kunststoffen (GFK) zzzg, 2006 DIN Beuth Verlag Berlin
- [24] DIN EN 1992-1 Eurocode 2: Bemessung und Konstruktion von Stahlbeton- und Spannbetontragwerken – Teil 1-1: Allgemeine Bemessungsregeln und Regeln für den Hochbau, 2004 Beuth Verlag Berlin
- [25] DIN EN 705:1994-08 Rohre und Formstücke aus glasfaserverstärkten duroplastischen Kunststoffen (GFK). Verfahren zur Regressionsanalyse und deren Anwendung. DIN Beuth Verlag, Berlin
- [26] DIN EN ISO 9080:2003: Kunststoff-Rohrleitungs- und Schutzsysteme – Bestimmung des Zeitstand-Innendruckverhaltens von thermoplastischen Rohrwerkstoffen durch Extrapolation DIN Beuth Verlag, Berlin
- [27] CSA S807 10: Specification for fibre-reinforced polymers Mississauga, CSA Canada 2010
- [28] Knab, F., Weber, A., Schweinfurth, J.: Sicherer Einsatz von Glasfaserbewehrung im Bauwesen. Hinweise und Anwendungsbeispiele für die Praxis. Beton- und Stahlbetonbau 2015, S. 822–831.
- [29] Weber, A.: Prüfungskonzepte für Bewehrungsmaterialien mit zeitabhängigen Widerständen, Bauingenieur 91 (2018)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Parts of this paper are originated from committee work, which not has been funded.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.